

Digital Culpability and Platform Liability in Nigeria: Analysing Principal-Agent Dynamics in Data Protection after Femi Falana v Meta

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ABSTRACT: This paper examines the doctrine of principal-agent relationship and its implications for liability arising from personal data violations under Nigerian law. Underscoring the new phenomenon of digital culpability, the article undertakes a critical analysis of the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 and the General Application and Implementation Directive (GAID) 2025, with particular reference to judicial reasoning in Femi Falana v Meta Platforms Inc. The study interrogates the extent to which digital platforms, operating as intermediaries, may incur liability as principals for the acts of third parties within the data processing ecosystem. It further evaluates how Nigerian courts address issues of jurisdiction, attribution of liability, and enforcement challenges in cross-border data protection disputes. The paper argues that Nigerian law is progressively expanding the scope of vicarious liability in data protection, especially in circumstances where digital platforms exercise substantial control over the means and purposes of data processing. It concludes that a purposive and technologically responsive application of agency principle is essential to ensure effective protection of privacy rights in Nigeria's evolving digital environment.

Keywords: *Digital Culpability, Principal–Agent Relationship, Platform Liability, Data Protection, Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA) 2023*

1. Introduction

The rapid expansion of digital technologies and online platforms has fundamentally reshaped traditional legal conceptions of agency and liability. In contemporary digital environments, interactions are no longer confined to bilateral relationships but instead occur within complex, multi-layered networks involving platform providers, users, data processors and third-party actors. This structural shift has generated significant legal uncertainty, particularly in relation to the attribution of responsibility for wrongful acts involving personal data. In Nigeria, these developments have necessitated a re-examination of established legal doctrines, especially the doctrine of principal–agent relationship, within the context of data protection law as well as the entire relationship between technology and law.

The enactment of the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 (NDPA) represents a major legislative response to these challenges. The Act establishes a comprehensive framework for the protection of personal data, setting out principles governing lawful processing, delineating the roles of data controllers and data processors. The Act also provides mechanisms for enforcement and redress. Central to the Act is the imposition of obligations on entities that determine the purposes and means of data processing, as well as those that process data on their behalf. In doing so, the NDPA implicitly reflects the traditional principal–agent structure, with data controllers occupying a position analogous to principals and data processors functioning as agents acting under instruction.

Notwithstanding this statutory framework, significant questions remain regarding the scope of liability or what we call digital culpability, where personal data violations occur through intermediaries, particularly digital platforms such as social media networks. These platforms typically host and disseminate user-generated content while simultaneously exercising varying degrees of control over data processing activities from the backend, including content moderation, algorithmic prioritisation and targeted advertising. This dual role complicates the application of conventional

legal principles. On the one hand, platforms present themselves as neutral intermediaries that merely facilitate communication between users; on the other hand, their operational control over the architecture of data flows suggests a level of authority consistent with that of a principal. This presents a paradox that is the central thesis of this article.

This article is structured into eight segments: the Introduction, Conceptual Framework, Legal Framework for Data Protection in Nigeria, Principal–Agent Dynamics in Data Processing, Doctrinal Significance of *Femi Falana v Meta Platforms Inc*, Control, Agency and Expanding Platform Liability, Intermediary Liability and the Limits of Safe Harbour, and the Conclusion. As noted earlier, we employed doctrinal approach to enable us analyse the statutes and judicial cases as primary and secondary sources of data to underscore the legal principles and the digital reality of data processing in the midst of data privacy concerns.

2. Conceptual Framework

This section provides a conceptual foundation by clarifying the principal terms and concepts that underpin the discussion in this article.

2.1. Personal Data

Section 65 of the NDPA 2023 defines personal data as ‘any information relating to an individual, who can be identified or is identifiable, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, psychological, cultural, social, or economic identity of that individual’.

In the same vein, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), Nigerian Data Protection Regulation 2019 defines “Personal Data” to mean: any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that

natural person; It can be anything from a name, address, a photo, an email address, bank details, posts on social networking websites, medical information, and other unique identifier such as but not limited to MAC address, IP address, IMEI number, IMSI number, SIM and others.

The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) also provides a comprehensive definition of personal data. Article 4(1), provides that:

"'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person."

While the definitions under the NDPA 2023, the NDPR 2019 and the GDPR appear largely convergent, they differ subtly in emphasis. The Nigerian framework, though inspired by the GDPR, incorporates identifiers unique to the African digital context, such as SIM and IMEI numbers. These variations in national definitions and regulatory standards between national governments, have significant implications for international trade, digital sovereignty and the harmonization of data protection regimes.

2.2. Data Protection/Data Privacy

Data protection refers to the legal, regulatory, technical and organisational framework governing the processing of personal data and safeguarding such data against unauthorised access, misuse, alteration, loss, destruction, or other forms of unlawful processing. In Nigeria, it derives normative support from the constitutional right to privacy and receives statutory expression under the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, which regulates personal data processing and defines personal data as information relating to an identified or identifiable individual.

Although the terms data privacy and data protection are often used interchangeably, they are more accurately understood as distinct but overlapping concepts. As

Makulilo observes, *privacy and data protection are ‘two distinct and separate concepts although they have overlapping objectives, and the difference between them lies in their scope, goals and content. In this sense, data privacy is primarily concerned with the individual’s interest in autonomy, confidentiality and control over personal information, whereas data protection is broader and encompasses the legal and institutional safeguards, as well as the technical and organisational measures, that govern the collection, use, storage, disclosure and security of personal data.*

2.3. Data Controller and Data Processor

The data controller is an entity responsible for determining the purposes and means of processing personal data. Section 65 of the NDPA 2023 defines a data controller as any ‘individual, private entity, public Commission, agency or any other body who, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of processing of personal data’. Controllers bear the primary legal and ethical responsibility for compliance with data protection obligations. They must ensure that personal data is collected and processed lawfully, fairly, transparently, and that data subjects can exercise their rights effectively. Controllers are also accountable for implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard personal data.

Whereas, Data processors are entities that process personal data on behalf of a controller. Section 65 of the NDPA defines a data processor to mean “*an individual, private entity, public authority, or any other body, who processes personal data on behalf of or at the direction of a data controller or another data processor.*” Unlike controllers, processors do not determine the purpose or means of processing but have statutory obligations to implement security measures, maintain processing records and assist controllers in ensuring compliance with data subject rights. Processors may be internal departments within an organization or external service providers, such as cloud service providers, data hosting companies and IT support vendors. The Act imposes obligations on processors to act only on lawful instructions from controllers and they are liable for breaches arising from negligence or failure to follow security protocols.

2.4. Principal–Agent Relationship in Law

The doctrine of principal–agent relationship constitutes a foundational pillar of private law, particularly in the allocation of rights, duties and liabilities arising from transactions conducted through intermediaries. At its core, an agency relationship arises where one party, the agent, is authorised to act on behalf of another, the principal, in such a manner as to affect the principal’s legal position in relation to third parties. In the case of *Nigeria Progress Ltd v. North-East Line Corporation*, the Supreme Court defined an agency relation by stating that:

“Agency can be defined as the consensual relationship which arises when a person called the agent acts on behalf of another called the principal whereby the latter becomes answerable for the lawful acts of the former, carried out within the scope of his authority as to affect the legal relations between the principal and a third party.”

The Apex court went further to state that:

“A relation of agency is generally said to exist whenever one person called the ‘agent’ has authority to act on behalf of another called the ‘principal’ and consents to act. Whenever that relationship exists in any situation depends not on the precise terminology employed by the parties to describe their relationship, but on the true nature of the agreement, or the exact circumstances of the relationship between the alleged principal and agent.”

This authority may be expressly conferred or implied from the conduct of the parties, and once established, the acts of the agent are within the scope of that authority, such acts are treated in law as the acts of the principal.

Under Nigerian agency law, a principal may be bound by the acts of an agent acting with actual authority, whether express or implied, or with apparent (ostensible) authority; and, in appropriate cases, a principal or employer may also incur vicarious liability for wrongful acts committed by the agent or servant in the course of the agency or employment. Actual authority refers to the authority that the principal has expressly or impliedly granted to the agent. Where an agent acts within the scope of such authority, the principal is bound by the agent’s acts, irrespective of whether the

principal directly participated in the transaction. Apparent authority, on the other hand, arises where the principal, by words or conduct, represents to a third party that the agent has authority to act, thereby estopping the principal from denying such authority. This doctrine is particularly significant in situations where third parties rely on the outward manifestations of authority rather than the internal arrangements between principal and agent.

Closely related to these concepts is the doctrine of vicarious liability, which imposes culpability on a principal for wrongful acts committed by an agent in the course of employment or within the scope of authorised activities. The justification for vicarious liability lies in considerations of control, enterprise risk, and fairness; it reflects the idea that a principal who benefits from the activities of an agent should also bear the risks associated with those activities. Nigerian courts have consistently upheld this principle, emphasising that liability may arise where there is a sufficient connection between the agent's conduct and the authorised enterprise.

In data protection law, traditional agency principles are reflected in the NDPA 2023 through the distinction between data controllers and data processors. The data controller resembles a principal because it determines the purposes and means of processing, while the data processor resembles an agent because it acts on the controller's instructions. However, this framework becomes more complex in modern digital environments, where platforms often exercise shared or overlapping control over data processing. As a result, the strict principal-agent analogy is not always sufficient and liability must be assessed through a more flexible and context-sensitive approach. It is therefore necessary to examine the legal position regulating the relationship between data controllers and data processors, and the liabilities attributable to each within that framework.

3. Legal Framework for Data Protection in Nigeria

The legal framework for data protection in Nigeria comprises constitutional provisions, sector-specific legislation and regulatory instruments. For the purpose of this discussion, however, attention is confined to the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 and the General Application and Implementation Directive (GAID) 2025.

3.1 Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023

The NDPA 2023 constitutes the principal legislative instrument governing the protection of personal data in Nigeria. The Act gave effect to the constitutional right to privacy and establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework that defines the obligations of data controllers and data processors, while simultaneously providing enforceable rights and remedies for data subjects.

At the heart of the NDPA are the core principles governing the processing of personal data. Section 24 of the Act provides that personal data must be processed in a lawful, fair and transparent manner. This requirement reflects a fundamental shift from unregulated data practices to a rights-based approach that prioritises the dignity and autonomy of data subjects. The principle of lawfulness ensures that data processing is grounded in a recognised legal basis, while fairness and transparency impose obligations of openness and accountability on data handlers.

In addition to these foundational principles, the Act imposes stringent obligations on data controllers, who bear primary responsibility for ensuring compliance with its provisions. Section 29 requires controllers to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to guarantee the security, integrity and confidentiality of personal data. These measures are designed to mitigate risks associated with data breaches and unauthorised processing, thereby reinforcing the duty of care owed to data subjects. The emphasis on accountability further underscores the central role of the controller as the entity ultimately responsible for the data processing lifecycle.

The NDPA also recognises the rights of data subjects as a critical component of its regulatory framework. Under Part VI of the Act, individuals are granted a range of enforceable rights, including the right to access personal data, the right to rectification, the right to erasure, and the right to object to processing. These rights are accompanied by mechanisms for redress, including the ability to lodge complaints and seek judicial remedies in cases of infringement. In this regard, the Act adopts a rights-centric approach that aligns with international data protection standards.

Of particular significance to the present discourse is section 53 of the Act, which introduces the concept of joint and vicarious liability. This provision stipulates that where multiple entities are involved in the processing of personal data, they may be held jointly liable for any breach of the Act. The implication of this provision is that liability is not confined to the entity that directly commits the wrongful act but may extend to other actors within the data processing chain whose conduct contributed to the violation.

This statutory recognition of joint and vicarious liability represents a critical intersection between data protection law and the doctrine of principal–agent relationship. By allowing liability to be attributed across multiple actors, the NDPA acknowledges the complex and interconnected nature of modern data processing systems. In particular, it provides a legal basis for holding data controllers, analogous to principals, responsible for the acts of data processors and other intermediaries acting on their behalf.

Accordingly, section 53 can be understood as an explicit incorporation of agency principles into the statutory framework of data protection in Nigeria. It reflects the broader policy objective of ensuring that entities with control over data processing cannot evade responsibility by delegating functions to third parties. In this sense, the provision strengthens accountability within the data protection framework and enhances the protection of data subjects’ rights.

3.2 General Application and Implementation Directive (GAID) 2025

The GAID 2025 serves as a critical regulatory instrument designed to operationalise and clarify the provisions of the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023. The Guideline was issued by the Nigeria Data Protection Commission pursuant to its statutory mandate, the GAID provides interpretative guidance and establishes practical standards for compliance within Nigeria’s evolving data protection ecosystem.

One of the most significant contributions of the GAID lies in its articulation of a general duty of care applicable to all entities engaged in the processing of personal data. Article 2(a) emphasises that every person, body, or authority involved in data processing owes a duty to data subjects to carefully assess the context of such

processing and ensure that it aligns with the constitutional right to privacy. This duty extends beyond mere formal compliance with statutory provisions and requires a proactive evaluation of risks, purposes, and potential impacts on the rights and freedoms of individuals. In effect, it reinforces the accountability principle embedded in the NDPA by imposing a continuous obligation of diligence on data handlers.

The GAID further strengthens the regulatory framework by affirming the extraterritorial application of Nigerian data protection law. Article 1 provides that the NDPA applies not only to entities domiciled or operating within Nigeria but also to foreign data controllers and processors who process the personal data of individuals located in Nigeria. This provision reflects an acknowledgment of the global nature of data flows and seeks to prevent regulatory gaps that could arise from the cross-border operations of digital platforms. By extending the reach of the law beyond territorial boundaries, the GAID enhances the capacity of the Nigerian legal system to address data protection violations involving multinational corporations.

In addition, the GAID places considerable emphasis on the implementation of technical and organisational safeguards as a means of ensuring data security and compliance. Article 2(d) requires data controllers and processors to take into account the characteristics of data, such as its value, volume, and sensitivity and to adopt appropriate measures to mitigate associated risks. These measures include the deployment of secure processing systems, regular monitoring and evaluation of data protection practices, and the establishment of internal compliance mechanisms. Such requirements underscore the preventive dimension of data protection law, shifting the focus from reactive enforcement to proactive risk management.

Beyond these specific obligations, the GAID underscores the importance of situating data processing activities within their broader material context. It requires data controllers to assess whether the purposes and methods of processing are consistent with constitutional guarantees, particularly the right to privacy enshrined in section 37 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999. This contextual approach recognises that data protection cannot be reduced to technical compliance alone but must be understood in relation to fundamental rights and societal values.

Taken together, these provisions significantly expand the scope and depth of the NDPA. They not only clarify the obligations of data controllers and processors but also reinforce the underlying principles of accountability, responsibility, and rights protection. From the perspective of agency law, the GAID further strengthens the analogy between data controllers and principals by emphasising their overarching duty of care and their responsibility for ensuring compliance across the data processing chain. In doing so, it provides an important normative foundation for attributing liability in cases involving complex, multi-actor data processing arrangements, including those involving digital platforms.

3.3 The NDPC Guidance Notice on Registration of Data Controllers and Data Processors of Major Importance

The regulatory framework on data protection in Nigeria is further strengthened by the Guidance Notice on the Registration of Data Controllers and Data Processors of Major Importance and All Matters Connected Therewith 2024 issued by the NDPC. While the guideline is not a primary legislation, the Guidance Notice is important because it gives practical effect to sections 5(d), 44, 45 and 65 of the NDPA 2023. It identifies the categories of data controllers and data processors that are regarded as being of major importance and are therefore subject to registration and heightened compliance obligations.

Under the Guidance Notice, a data controller or data processor may be designated as being of major importance where it keeps or has access to a filing system for personal data and among other things, processes the personal data of more than 200 data subjects within six months, provides commercial ICT services on digital devices belonging to others, or operates in sectors considered significant to the economy, society or security of Nigeria, such as communication, education, finance, health, insurance, e-commerce, and public service. The Notice then classifies such entities into three categories, namely Ultra-High Level, Extra-High Level, and Ordinary-High Level, based on factors such as the sensitivity of the data, the volume of data processed, reliance on cloud or third-party servers, cross-border data flows and the degree of technical control exercised over processing operations.

Of particular relevance to the question of principal-agent liability is paragraph 5 of the Notice, which restates section 29(1)(a) of the Act and makes it mandatory for a data controller who engages a data processor, or for a processor who engages another processor, to ensure that the engaged processor complies with the principles and obligations applicable under the Act. This provision reinforces the accountability structure of the Nigerian data protection regime by making it clear that responsibility does not end with delegation. In effect, the controller remains under a continuing duty to supervise and ensure the compliance of the processor, a position that closely mirrors the traditional principal-agent relationship in which the principal may incur liability for acts carried out within its operational framework.

The Guidance Notice is also significant in the context of digital platforms. It expressly places public social media app developers and proprietors within the Ultra-High Level category of major data processing. This is an important indicator that digital platform operators are viewed by the Commission as entities with heightened obligations, especially where they process large volumes of personal data, rely on technological infrastructure under their control, and are substantially involved in cross-border data flows. Accordingly, the Notice supports the argument that where a digital platform determines the conditions of processing and engages other actors in the data chain, liability may properly extend beyond the immediate processor to the controller or platform proprietor that retains ultimate control and derives benefit from the processing operation.

The Guidance Notice therefore strengthens the argument that, in Nigerian data protection law, the engagement of a processor does not absolve the controller of responsibility; rather, it confirms a continuing duty of oversight that is analogous to the responsibility of a principal for acts carried out within the sphere of delegated authority.

4. Principal–Agent Dynamics in Data Processing

The regulatory framework established by the NDPA and the GAID reflects a deliberate alignment with traditional agency principles, particularly in the allocation of responsibility within the data processing system. Taken together, these instruments affirm that data controllers occupy a position analogous to principals. The Data

controller bears ultimate responsibility for determining the purposes and means of processing personal data, while data processors function in a capacity similar to agents, acting on behalf of and under the instructions of controllers.

Under the NDPA, the defining feature of a data controller is the exercise of decisive control over the objectives and modalities of data processing. This control is not merely formal but substantive, it encompasses decisions on the collection, use, storage and dissemination of personal data. As such, the controller assumes primary responsibility for ensuring compliance with the principles of lawful processing, accountability and data security. In contrast, data processors are engaged to carry out specific processing activities on behalf of controllers, typically within the confines of contractual or statutory instructions. Although processors do not ordinarily determine the purposes of processing, the NDPA nonetheless imposes direct obligations on them, thereby recognising that liability may arise independently of the controller in certain circumstances.

The GAID reinforces this structure by emphasising the overarching duty of care owed by all entities involved in data processing and by requiring controllers to exercise continuous oversight over processing activities. This supervisory role further underscores the analogy with agency law, where principals are expected to monitor and control the actions of their agents to ensure compliance with legal and fiduciary obligations. Moreover, the recognition of joint and vicarious liability under the NDPA indicates that responsibility may extend across the data processing chain, particularly where the actions of a processor are closely connected to the controller's mandate.

Notwithstanding this seemingly coherent framework, the emergence of digital platforms introduces significant complexity into the principal-agent dynamic. Platforms such as social media networks operate within a hybrid model that defies straightforward classification. On one level, they present themselves as neutral intermediaries that merely host and transmit user-generated content. This characterisation aligns with the notion of agency neutrality, suggesting that platforms should not be held liable for content created by third parties in the absence of direct involvement or knowledge. The courts in Nigeria have been confronted with similar

position, that calls for judicial interpretation of the position of the data protection law of the liability of data controller and processor.

In the case of Femi Falana, SAN v Meta Platforms Inc, the applicant brought a fundamental rights action against Meta Platforms after discovering on 16 January 2025 that a video using his name, still image and motion image had been posted on a page styled “AfriCare Health Centre” on Facebook. The video allegedly stated that he had suffered from prostatitis for 16 years. The applicant, Falana stated that the publication was false, misleading, offensive and an invasion of his private life. He further stated that he has never had such a condition and had never dealt with Meta or that page on any health issue.

The respondent contended that they did not create or post the video, that the publication was made by a third party. That Meta Platforms Inc functioned only as an intermediary hosting provider and that it removed the video on 25 April 2025 when it became aware of it, before service of the originating process. Meta also argued that the claim was really a tort claim dressed up as a fundamental-rights claim.

The Applicant, argued on digital-platform liability, that Meta went beyond passive hosting. That Meta continued to publish his name and image in a false health-related context. That the publication was unfair, inaccurate, misleading and insensitive. That the false publication boosted traffic and advertising revenue and that respondent violated both section 37 of the Constitution and section 24(1)(a) and (e) of the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023.

The respondent argued four main points relevant to agency and vicarious liability. First, it argued that Meta Platform Inc was only an intermediary service provider and not the author of the content. Secondly, it was contended that the respondent could not be held liable for content posted by a third party unless it had been properly notified and then failed to act. Third, it relied on the idea that the claim was essentially tortious and therefore wrongly framed as a fundamental-rights application. Fourth, it maintained that when the Respondent became aware of the content, they removed it and so continued responsibility should not attach.

The court expressly addressed Meta’s attempt to rely on the fact that the publication was made by an unnamed third party. It stated that Meta (Respondent) “is presumed to be acting on behalf of an unnamed or undisclosed principal” and then invoked the settled principle of agency that the act of an agent binds the principal and vice versa. The court then reasoned that where the identity of the third party who posted the video has not been revealed, the platform can be sued for the publication appearing on its website. In substance, the court treated Meta as the visible actor in the legal relationship and refused to let it hide behind an undisclosed user. That is the agency-based foundation of the judgment.

The court rejected the idea that the Respondent could rely on a pure innocent-dissemination or third-party-content defence. It held that the defence of innocent dissemination and *jus tertii* was not available because Meta was not a bare passive host. The court relied on Meta’s Terms of Service, community standards and operational control, stating that Meta had both actual and constructive knowledge of publications sent into its platform. The court also said Meta owed a correlative obligation to ensure that content posted by undisclosed third parties was not incompatible with the constitutional rights of others.

The court further held that in the absence of credible proof that the Respondent lacked actual or constructive knowledge, they should be deemed a joint controller of the data and information published in violation of Falana’s privacy. It held that the Respondent breached section 24(1)(a) and (e) of the NDPA 2023 and was in breach of a duty of care to ensure the accuracy and integrity of publications on its platform. It said the risk of inaccuracy and privacy violation was foreseeable and that a global technology company ought to have provided adequate safeguards. The court granted reliefs on privacy and NDPA breach and awarded damages of US\$25,000,000 in favour of the Applicant.

5. Doctrinal Significance of Femi Falana v Meta Platforms

The decision in *Femi Falana v Meta Platforms* is significant for Nigerian data protection law because the court moved beyond a narrow intermediary model and examined platform liability through the lenses of control, agency and responsibility. The court first rejected the Respondent’s preliminary objection founded on Section

97 of the Sheriffs and Civil Process Act, holding that a fundamental rights action commenced by originating motion is sui generis and is not caught by the statutory endorsement requirement applicable to writs of summons.

On the merits, the court declined to treat Meta as a merely passive host of third-party content. Although the impugned video was posted by an unidentified third party, the court held that the platform could still be sued where the publication appeared on its system and the identity of the immediate poster had not been disclosed. In doing so, the court invoked agency reasoning, treating the platform-user relationship as sufficiently proximate to justify proceeding against the platform notwithstanding the presence of an undisclosed actor behind the publication.

In holding that the Respondent were vicariously liable for the publication on its platform. The Court reasoned that the defence of innocent dissemination, as well as reliance on *jus tertii*, was unavailable in circumstances where the platform's Terms of Service, community standards, and moderation architecture gave it at least constructive knowledge of the publication environment on its platform. The judgment therefore treats platform design, content governance, and the commercial benefit derived from publication as relevant factors in attributing legal responsibility.

More importantly, the court linked this reasoning to data protection law. It characterised Meta as a joint controller of the data and information disseminated through the impugned publication and held that the continued publication breached the applicant's constitutional right to privacy as well as section 24(1)(a) and (e) of the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, which require personal data to be processed fairly, lawfully and accurately. While the High Court decision, is presently been appeal, the decision represents one of the clearest Nigerian judicial statements that digital platforms may incur liability for third-party content where control, knowledge, and failure to prevent or remedy the publication are sufficiently established.

6. Control, Agency and Expanding Platform Liability

The statutory provisions of the NDPA 2023 supports a broader attribution of responsibility than classical bilateral models of agency might suggest. The Act

distinguishes between data controllers and data processors, but it also recognises that liability may extend across the chain of processing, particularly through section 53, which contemplates joint and vicarious liability. Read together with the GAID 2025, which imposes a duty of care on every person, body, or authority involved in processing personal data, the Nigerian framework is increasingly oriented towards accountability rather than formalistic role-labelling.

This accountability-centred approach is consistent with comparative data protection law. Under the GDPR, a controller is the person or body that determines, alone or jointly with others, the purposes and means of processing. The European Data Protection Board has likewise stressed that controllership is a functional concept centred on factual influence and effective participation in processing decisions. The decisions of the Court of Justice of the European Union in *Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein GmbH and Fashion ID GmbH & Co. KG v Verbraucherzentrale NRW eV* further demonstrate that an actor may be treated as a joint controller even where it does not exclusively create the impugned content, provided it participates in determining the conditions under which the data are collected, transmitted, or otherwise processed.

The case of Fashion ID GmbH & Co. KG decided by the Court of Justice of the European Union on 29 July 2019. a German online clothing retailer, Fashion ID, which embedded the Facebook “Like” button on its website. Because of that plugin, visitors’ personal data could be automatically transmitted to Facebook Ireland, even if the visitors were not Facebook members. The consumer protection association Verbraucherzentrale NRW challenged Fashion ID, arguing that the company transmitted users’ personal data to Facebook without proper consent and without giving users the required data-protection information.

The main legal question was whether Fashion ID could be treated as a data controller under EU data protection law for the data collected and sent to Facebook through the plugin. The Court held that Fashion ID was not responsible for Facebook’s later use of the data after the data had already been sent to Facebook. However, Fashion ID

could be considered a joint controller with Facebook for the earlier stage, the collection of visitors' personal data and the transmission of that data to Facebook.

The reason was that Fashion ID benefited commercially from using the Facebook "Like" button because it increased visibility and advertising for its goods. Facebook also benefited because it could use the data for its own commercial purposes. The Court also ruled that Fashion ID had duties as a joint controller. It had to inform website visitors, at the time their data was collected, about matters such as its identity and the purposes of the processing. If consent was required, Fashion ID had to obtain consent before the collection and transmission of the data.

Against that background, the reasoning in Falana case is doctrinally defensible. Where a platform controls the architecture of visibility, retention, targeting and removal of content, it becomes increasingly artificial to describe it as wholly external to the processing operation. In such circumstances, the language of agency and vicarious liability remains useful, but it must be adapted to the realities of platform governance, where power is exercised algorithmically and contractually rather than through traditional face-to-face supervision.

7. Intermediary Liability and the Limits of Safe Harbour

The principal weakness in Nigerian law is not the absence of legal tools for platform responsibility, but the absence of a clear statutory intermediary-liability regime. Unlike the United States, where section 230 (c) (1) of the Communications Decency Act confers broad immunity on providers of interactive computer services, the section provides that "No provider or user of an interactive computer service shall be treated as the publisher or speaker of any information provided by another information content provider." The Act under Section 230(c)(2)(A) further provides protection where an online service removes or restricts objectionable content. The section provides that:

"No provider or user of an interactive computer service shall be held liable on account of—(A) any action voluntarily taken in good faith to restrict access to or availability of material that the provider or user considers to be obscene, lewd,

lascivious, filthy, excessively violent, harassing, or otherwise objectionable, whether or not such material is constitutionally protected...”

Section 230 generally means that an online platform, website, or internet service provider is not treated as the legal publisher or speaker of content posted by another person. For example, if a user posts defamatory or unlawful content, the platform may be protected from liability for merely hosting that user-generated content. However, the protection is not unlimited. The statute says it does not block enforcement of federal criminal law, intellectual property law, communications privacy law, and certain sex-trafficking-related claims.

In the same vein, among the European Union, the E-Commerce Directive - Conditional Safe-Harbour Protections and now the Digital Services Act- Conditional Safe-Harbour Protections establish conditional safe-harbour protections tied to knowledge and expeditious removal. Article 14 of the “No general obligation to monitor where an information society service provides the transmission of information via a communication network, and it does not actively initiate or select the transmitted data, it shall not be liable for the information stored, unless, after obtaining knowledge, it fails to act expeditiously to remove or disable access to that information.” Similar provision is also provided under Article 6 of the Digital Services Act. NDPA does not expressly codify intermediary immunity for digital platforms.

This silence creates uncertainty. On one view, the absence of explicit immunity makes it easier to argue that a platform exercising significant control over dissemination, recommendation, moderation and monetisation should bear responsibility for unlawful data processing occurring through its system. On another view, the lack of legislative clarity risks inconsistent adjudication and may encourage courts to import broad intermediary immunities by analogy. The better approach is a calibrated one: immunity, where recognised, should be conditional and should not extend to platforms that exercise substantial control over the processing environment or that fail to act after acquiring actual or constructive knowledge of unlawful activity.

In that sense, Falana Case is best understood not as abolishing intermediary protection, but as narrowing its availability in cases where the platform's involvement is too significant to justify the fiction of neutrality. That conclusion is consistent with the broader literature on platform power, which emphasises that platforms increasingly shape speech, information flows, and data extraction in ways that call for corresponding legal accountability.

8. Conclusion

The relationship between principal-agent doctrine and data protection law in Nigeria is no longer merely theoretical. The NDPA 2023 and the GAID 2025 provide a framework in which responsibility may extend beyond the immediate actor to those who exercise control over the purposes, means, and conditions of data processing and this control is not merely physical but may include algorithmic manipulation that happens beneath the data process. *Femi Falana v Meta Platforms* illustrates this development in concrete terms: the court rejected a purely neutral-intermediary conception of platform responsibility, invoked agency reasoning, imposed vicarious liability, and treated the platform as a joint controller in relation to the impugned publication.

The broader implication is that Nigerian data protection law is moving towards a more realistic account of digital power. That shift is both welcome and necessary. Modern platforms do not merely host content, they organise, prioritise, amplify and monetise it. A legal framework that ignores these functions would fail to protect privacy effectively in the digital age. At the same time, the law must develop in a principled manner. Greater doctrinal clarity is needed on the precise circumstances in which intermediary protection should yield to agency-based or controller-based liability, and stronger mechanisms are required for the cross-border enforcement of privacy rights.

Ultimately, the future effectiveness of Nigeria's data protection regime will depend on whether courts and regulators continue to interpret existing legal doctrines in a technologically responsive manner. In the new right-based world order, the marriage between law and technology have to be strengthened. Law cannot afford to trail

scientific and technological advancement. To ensure real justice, the two must at least grow together. In the Nigerian data protection framework, the foundation has been laid by the NDPA, the GAID, and the judicial reasoning in Falana; what remains is the task of developing a coherent jurisprudence of platform accountability that is at once protective of rights, fair to regulated entities and responsive to the realities of digital data governance.

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